
A STUDY ON EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT, INTELLIGENCE AND MENTAL ABILITIES OF RURAL AND URBAN SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Academic achievement is the accomplishment or acquired proficiency in the performance of an individual in a given skill or body of knowledge. It is level of performance in school subject as exhibited by an individual. In the school setting it is referred to as the exhibition of knowledge attained or skills development in school subject. Test scores or marks assigned by high or low which means that 5 academic achievements could either be good or bad. Academic achievement is a key mechanism through which students learn about their talents, abilities and competence which are an important part of developing career aspiration and academic achievement in adolescence an often correlated. Today we are living in the globalization where our traditional ways of living are in changing phase. All the societies and its members are facing tough competition due to privation, urbanization the youth is in a problem where they find themselves unfit, a rapid change in family life, pressure of peers and society. Some scholar have hold that intelligence is essential the quicker individual is able to adjust and adopt himself to his new environment the more intelligence he the intelligence is the ability to learn it is through intelligence that individual learn and gains experiences, and hence the more an individual is able to take advance of his past experience in facing future life, then he is more intelligent.

INTRODUCTION:-

The main focus of education process is to improve the performance of learning of the student. The learning outcomes of the students are measured with the help of their achievement of performance. Performance assessment is the process of measuring terminal behaviors of students at the end of instruction. It is the job of the teacher to measure whether the students have acquired the concept of achievement before proceeding with the instruction which arranges these concepts in paper relationship for the learning of the principal. The achievement is the end product of the instruction usually verbal performance. Achievement encompasses student ability and performance, it is multidimensional, it is intricately related to human growth and cognitive emotional, social, and physical development, it reflects the whole child, it is not related to a single instance but occurs across time and levels, through a student life in public school and on into post-secondary years and working life (Steinberger 1993). According to Smith and Spence 1983 defined achievement motivation as task oriented behavior that allows individuals' performance to be evaluated according to some internally or externally imposed criteria that involves the individual in competing with others or that otherwise involves some standard of excellence.

Academic Achievement:-

Academic achievement is the accomplishment or acquired proficiency in the performance of an individual in a given skill or body of knowledge. Academic achievement means knowledge attained and skill development in school subject usually designed by test score or by marks assigned by teacher or both. Academic achievement is the criterion for selection, promotion or recognition in various walks of life. Academic achievement is the maximum performance in all activities at school after a period of training. Webster defines achievement as the quality and quantity of a student's work. Academic achievement is generally regarded as the display of knowledge attained or skills developed in the school subject (Busuri 2000).

Learners characteristics:-

- Mental maturity/intellectual.
- Physical maturity as related to psychomotor abilities.

- Affective characteristics interest, motive attitude,value, emotional & expressive.
- Health/physique
- Self-concept
- Perception of situation
- Age
- Sex
- Mental health

Learners and teachers behavior: - All interaction in teaching to earning cognitive verbalizing psychomotor doing and affective feelings.

Group Characteristics:-

- ❖ Number
- ❖ Structure
- ❖ Attitude
- ❖ Cohesiveness
- ❖ Leaders

Physical Characteristic:-

- ❖ Space
- ❖ Duration
- ❖ Equipment

Outside forces:-

❖ **Condition Affecting Pupils**

1. Home
2. Neighborhood
3. Broad attitude influence

❖ **Condition Affecting Entire Setting:-**

1. Other teaching psychologists, supervisors.
2. Administration.
3. Curriculum requirement

4. Community expectation

REVIEW OF THE RELATED STUDIES:-

Anita N. Cha Trivedi, Vineeta (1988) in their study titled "The relationship of parental attitude, socio-economic background and the feeling of security among the intermediate student and their academic achievement" investigated that there existed a significant relationship among parental attitude, socio-economic status and academic achievement. **Garg, V.P. & Chaturvedi, Seema (1992)** in their research work "A study of intelligence and socio-economic status as correlates of academic performance" investigated that academic performance is related to socio-economic status and also has a linear correspondence.

POPULATION:-

Population is a statistical concept which means a group of large number of units from which a smaller group of some units is selected and used for achieving some purpose. "It is a large group scattered over a wide geographical area or a small group concealed in a limited narrow area." And the sample selected for this research study is as follows-

Gender	School		Total
	RURAL	URBAN	
BOYS	35	35	70
GIRLS	35	35	70
TOTAL			140

RESEARCH DESIGN :-

The term " design " means "Drawing an outline" or planning or arranging details. It is a process of making decision before the situation arises in which decision has to be actual out.

William Zikmund (1988) has described research design as 'A master plan specifically the method and procedures for collecting and analyzing the needed

information"An appropriate and efficient design must be prepared before research operation. The design help the researcher to organize his idea in a forum where by it will be possible for him to look for inadequate.

METHOD:-

For research work survey method is applied in two school in Rural area government school and Urban area government schools. Question are given to intelligence and academic achievement on each student All the question are prepared by different aspects.

RESEARCH DESIGN:-

Variables -

- **Independent**-Rural And Urban, Gender
- **Dependent**- Academic Achievement, Intelligence.

Tools -Intelligence, Academic Achievement Questionnaires

Statistical Analysis- Mean, SD,t-value

H-1 There will be significant difference in intelligence in rural and urban school student

{Df = 138 , t-value=18.45, P < 0.05}

Result –It is concluded there exists significant difference in the intelligence of rural and urban area school students.

H-2 There will be significant difference in SES in rural and urban school students.

{DF = 138 t-value=4.40, P < 0.05}

Result –It is concluded that there exists significant difference in the SES of rural and urban area school students.

H-3 There will be significant difference in Academic Achievement of boys and girls school students.

{DF = 138 , t-value = 0.02, P > 0.05}

Result- Concluded that there exists no significant difference in the Academic hievement of boys and girls school students.

SUGGESTIONS:-

The present study is helpful to teachers, parents and school administration in the following way.

- To start teachers should be committed to their student and their profession overall. in other words, strive to be a well-qualified and engaged teacher.
- Teachers should make democratic environment in the school.
- Regard each student as an individual and let him or her know that you care, respect their differences, while insisting on excellence.
- Encourage every student to dare to dream of what they might be.
- Provide information or strategies for students to cope with or avoid problems they may face at home or in the community which might otherwise keep them from achieving those dreams.

FOLLOW UP STUDIES:-

It is a fact that every search has a scope for research on this light the present study is not at a inclusive study after completion of the study, it was found that many important aspects of the study are to be taken care. These limitations are to be kept in mind and steps for betterment should taken by further researchers, if any similar type of study is to be conducted in future are

- To study the inter-relationship between intelligence and adjustment among senior secondary students.
- To study the effect of intelligence on academic achievement of government and private school students
- To study the effect of intelligence on academic achievement of government and BSP school students

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